

General methods

Melting points were determined (uncorrected) using electrical melting point apparatus, Electro-thermal 9300, USA. The infrared spectra were recorded in KBr disc by FT-IR spectrophotometer / Shimadzu. ¹H-NMR and ¹³C-NMR spectra were recorded using NMR Bruker 500 MHz-Avance III spectrometer and the chemical shifts were recorded in parts per million (ppm). Tetramethylsilane was used as the reference.

Chemical synthesis

Chemical synthesis of the intermediate (2-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-yl-thio) acetic acid

This compound is synthesized through S-alkylation reaction of 2-mercaptobenzothiazole with α -bromoacetic acid, and as follows;

To a stirred aqueous solution of α -bromoacetic acid (10mmol, 1.389g) in sodium hydroxide solution (10%, 10 mL), 2-mercaptobenzothiazole (10mmol, 1.6725g) in an aqueous solution of sodium hydroxide (10%, 10 mL) was added drop wise with continuous stirring. The mixture was refluxed for 3hrs and was then cooled and acidified with diluted hydrochloric acid to obtain a precipitate, which was filtered, washed excessively with distilled water and crystallized from ethanol to afford a yield of 90%, as white powder, m.p. 152-153 °C, as depicted on **Figure 1**.

FT-IR spectra recorded the following bands; 3110-2513 (str. vib. of OH of COOH), 3074 (Str. vib. of C-H aromatic ring), 2956-2896 (str. vib. of C-H aliph. (asym and sym)), 1714 (str. vib. of C=O of COOH), 1602-1581-1498 (str. vib. of C=C aromatic ring), 1315 (str. vib. of C=O of COOH).

General procedure for the synthesis of BZT-Linker (1A-E)

These compounds were prepared using the mixed anhydride method ¹⁷, as depicted in **Figure 1** and as follows;

The intermediate (2-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-yl-thio) acetic acid (10mmol) was suspended in dry chloroform (40ml) containing triethylamine (TEA, 10 mmol) and the mixture was cooled to (-5 to -8 °C) in an ice bath. Ethyl chloroformate (10 mmol) was added dropwise during 15 min and the mixture was stirred for further 15 min. The linker (10mmol) was dissolved in a cold distilled water containing TEA (10mmol) and was added immediately all at once with vigorous stirring for 1hr in an ice bath and for further 3hrs at room

temperature. A two-layered yellowish-orange solution was obtained, which was separated using a separator funnel and the aqueous layer was removed. The chloroform layer was washed with distilled water (3 x 20 ml) and was dried with anhydrous magnesium sulfate, filtered and evaporated under reduced pressure in a rotary evaporator to obtain yellowish-orange residues. The residues were washed with diethyl ether or petroleum ether few times to afford crystalline powder representing the resultant products (**1A-E**). These compounds were collected as follows:

BZT-Linker-Ala (1A) {(2-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-yl-thio) acetyl) alanine} ($C_{12}H_{12}O_3N_2S_2$, 296.36 g/mole) was synthesized starting from the intermediate (2-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-yl-thio) acetic acid) and L-Alanine (10mmol, 1.6g), as red crystalline powder, m.p. 165-167 °C with 79% yield. FT-IR spectra (ν , cm^{-1}) recorded the following characterized bands; 3461 (str. vib. of OH-COOH), 3419 (str. vib. of NH-amide), 2954-2905 (str. vib. of C-H aliph. (asym and sym)), 1712 (str. vib. of C=O of COOH), 1668 (str. vib. of C=O of amide), 1589-1573-1479 (str. vib. of C=C aromatic ring).

BZT-Linker-Cys (1B) {(2-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-yl-thio) acetyl) cysteine} ($C_{12}H_{12}O_3N_2S_3$, 328.42 g/mole) was prepared using L-Cysteine (10mmol, 1.2g) and collected as yellow crystalline powder, m.p. 175-177 °C with 85% yield. FT-IR spectra recorded the following bands; 3461 (str. vib. of OH-COOH), 3288 (str. vib. of NH-amide), 3062 (str. vib. of C-H aromatic ring), 2912-2871 (str. vib. of C-H aliph. (asym and sym)), 1714 (str. vib. of C=O of COOH), 1641 (str. vib. of C=O of amide), 1600-1545 (str. vib. of C=C aromatic ring).

Compound 1C {3-(2-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-yl-thio) acetamido) propionic acid} ($C_{12}H_{12}O_3N_2S_2$, 296.36) was prepared by reacting the intermediate with 3-Aminopropionic acid (10mmol, 1.6g) and collected as orange powder, m.p. 210-212 °C with 76% yield. FT-IR spectra recorded the following bands; 3442 (str. vib. of OH-COOH), 3225 (str. vib. of NH amide), 3050 (str. vib. of CH arom), 2987-2858 (str. vib. of C-H aliph. (asym and sym)), 1724 (str. vib. of C=O of COOH), 1631 (str. vib. of C=O of amide), 1600-1514 (str. vib. of C=C arom).

BZT-Linker-Aminohexanoic acid (1D) {6-(2-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-yl-thio) acetamido) hexanoic acid} ($C_{15}H_{18}O_3N_2S_2$, 338 g/mole) was prepared starting from the intermediate and 6-Aminohexanoic acid (10mmol, 1.31g) and collected as orange powder, m.p. 225-

227 °C with 90% yield. FT-IR spectra recorded the following bands; 3427 (str. vib. of OH-COOH), 3271(str. vib. of NH of amide), 3075 (str. vib. of C-H arom), 2983-2873 (str. vib. of C-H aliph. (asym and sym), 1737 (str. vib. of C=O of COOH),1629 (Str. vib. of C=O of amid),1612-1581 (str. vib. of C=C arom).

BZT-Linker-p-Aminobenzoic acid (1E) {4-(2-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-yl-thio) acetamido) benzoic acid (C₁₆H₁₂O₃N₂S₂, 344.4 g/mole)} was prepared from the intermediate and p-Amino-benzoic acid (10mmol, 1.37g) and collected as purple powder, m.p. 180-182 °C with 70% yield. FT-IR spectra recorded the following bands; 3430 (str. vib. of OH-COOH), 3330 (str. vib. of NH of amide), 3026 (str. vib. of C-H arom), 2981-2937 (str. vib. of C-H arom), 1703 (str. vib. of C=O of COOH), 1641(str. vib. of C=O of amide), 1598-1558-1479 (str. vib. of C=C arom).

General procedure for preparing the hybrid molecules (2A-E)

The target hybrid molecules were prepared starting with compounds **1A-E** and reacted with hydroxylamine to afford compounds **2A-E**, as depicted in **scheme 1**. This reaction was performed using the mixed anhydride method (**17**), as previously described.

Compounds **1A-E** (10mmol) in dry chloroform containing TEA (10mmol) was reacted with ECF (10mmol) and was then reacted with hydroxylamine. HCl (10mmol) in an aqueous solution (10ml) containing TEA (10mmol).

BZT-Linker-Ala Hydroxamate (2A) {2-(2-(benzo- [d]thiazol-2-yl-thio) acetamido)-N-Hydroxy- propanamide (C₁₂H₁₃O₃N₃S₂, 311.37 g/mole) was synthesized using compound **1A** (10mmol, 2.964 g) and was collected as yellow powder, m.p. 253-255 °C with 80% yield. FT-IR spectra recorded the following bands; 3452 (OH str. vib. of oxime), 3257 (NH str. vib. of oxime), 3200 (NH str. vib. of amide), 3058 (str. vib. of C-H arom), 2983-2852 (str. vib. of C-H aliph, asym and sym), 1699 (str. vib. of C=O of oxime),1616 (str. vib. of C=O of amide), 1610-1569 (str. vib. of C=C arom). ¹H-NMR spectra recorded the followings signals (ppm); 1.28 (doublet, 3H, CH₃), 4.25 (quartet, 1H, CH), 4.92 (singlet, 2H, CH₂), 7.40- 8.35 (multiplate, 4H, represent phenyl), 8.85 (singlet 1H, NH of amide group), 9.20 (singlet 1H, NH of oxime group), 10.96 (singlet, 1H, OH group). ¹³C-NMR spectra recorded the followings signals; 13.67 (CH₃), 34.59 (CH), 61.50 (CH₂), 111.91-125.83 (arom. CH), 152.58 (C=N of benzothiazole), 164.54 (C=O of amide), 168.08 (C=O of oxime).

BZT-Linker-Cys Hydroxamate (2B) {2-(2-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-yl-thio) acetamido)-N-hydroxy-3-mercapto propanamide (C₁₂H₁₃O₃N₃S₃, 343.43 g/mole) was synthesized starting from compound **1B** (10mmol, 3.284 g) and was collected as paige-colored powder, m.p. 235-237 °C with 77% yield. FT-IR spectra recorded the following characteristic bands; 3431 (str. vib. of OH-oxime), 3290 (NH str. vib. of oxime), 3114 (str. vib. of NH-amide), 3078 (str. vib. of C-H aromatic ring), 2964-2894 (str. vib. of C-H aliph. (asym and sym)), 1699 (str. vib. of C=O of oxime), 1639 (str. vib. of C=O of amide), 1596-1554-1496 (str. vib. of C=C arom.). ¹H-NMR spectra recorded the following signals; 3.48 (singlet, 1H, SH), 4.50 (triplet, 1H, CH), 4.13 (doublet, 2H, CH₂), 4.88 (singlet, 2H, CH₂), 7.37-8.10 (multiplate, 4H, phenyl), 8.27 (singlet, 1H, NH of amide group), 8.82 (singlet, 1H, NH of oxime group), 10.81 (singlet, 1H, OH group). ¹³C-NMR spectra recorded the following signals; 39.66 (CH₂-SH), 40.78 (CH), 41.23 (CH₂), 124,86-135.25 (CH arom), 153.32 (C=N of benzothiazole), 158.61 (C=O of amide), 167.27 (C=O of oxime).

BZT-Linker-Aminopropionic acid (2C) {3-(2-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-yl-thio) acetamido)-N-hydroxypropanamide (C₁₂H₁₃O₃N₃S₂, 311.37 g/mole)} was prepared starting from compound **1C** (10mmol, 2.964 g) and was collected as dark brown powder, m.p. 219-221 °C with 88% yield. FT-IR spectra recorded the following bands; 3315 (OH str. vib. of oxime), 3188 (NH str. vib. of oxime), 3112 (NH str. vib. of amide), 3053 (str. vib. of C-H arom.), 2981-2837 (str. vib. of C-H aliph. (asym and sym)), 1704 (str. vib. of C=O of oxime), 1679 (str. vib. of C=O of amide), 1600-1531-1500 (str. vib. of C=C arom.). ¹H-NMR spectra recorded the following signals; 2.16(triplet, 2H, CH₂-C=O), 3.58 (triplet, 2H, CH₂-N), 4.32(singlet, 2H, CH₂-S), 7.32-8.20 (multiplate, 4H, phenyl), 8.90 (singlet, 1H, NH of amide), 8.94 (singlet, 1H, NH of oxime), 9.86 (singlet, 1H, OH). ¹³C-NMR spectra recorded the following signals; 19.05 (CH₂-C=O), 38.30 (CH₂-N), 56.53 (CH₂-S), 119.31-129.34 (CH arom), 152.97 (C=N of benzothiazole), 166.37 (C=O of amide), 166.59 (C=O of oxime).

BZT-Linker-Aminohexanoic acid (2D) {6-(2-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-yl-thio) acetamido)-N-hydroxyhexanamide (C₁₅H₁₉O₃N₃S₂, 353.45 g/mol) was synthesized from compound **1D** (10mmol, 3.38 g) and was collected as chocolate-color powder, m.p. 269-271 °C with 85% yield. FT-IR spectra recorded the following bands; 34446 (str. vib. of OH-oxime),

3359 (str. vib. of NH-oxime), 3184 (NH str. vib. of amide), 3060 (str. vib. of C-H arom.), 2985-2918 (str. vib. of C-H aliph. (asym and sym), 1704 (str. vib. of C=O of oxime), 1649 (str. vib. of C=O of amide), 1599-1583 (str. vib. of C=C arom.). ¹H-NMR spectra recorded the following signals; 1.25-2.11 (Multiplet, 6H, 3(CH₂), 4.14 (triplet, 2H, CH₂-C=O), 4.19 (triplet, 2H, CH₂-N), 4.87 (singlet, 2H, CH₂-S), 7.35-8.05 (multiplet, 4H, phenyl), 8.32 (singlet, 1H, NH of amide), 8.86 (singlet, 1H, NH of oxime), 10.20 (singlet, 1H, OH). ¹³C-NMR spectra recorded the followings; 13.78 (CH₂), 18.25 (CH₂), 20.89 (CH₂), 24.60 (CH₂ C=O), 35.86 (CH₂-N), 55.86 (CH₂-S), 111.86-134.90 (CH arom), 151.03 (C=N of benzothiazole), 158.84 (C=O of amide), 162.32 (C=O of oxime).

BZT-Linker-p-Aminobenzoic acid Hydroxamate (2E) {4-(2-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-yl-thio)acetamido)-N-Hydroxy benzamide (C₁₆H₁₃O₃N₃S₂, 359.42 g/mole) was prepared starting from compound **1E** (10mmol, 3.44 g) and was collected as white powder, m.p. 280-282 °C with 90% yield. FT-IR spectra recorded the following bands; 3444 (OH str. vib. of oxime), 3404 (NH str. vib. of oxime), 3295 (NH str. vib. of oxime), 3022 (str. vib. of C-H arom), 2972-2925 (str. vib. of C-H aliph. (asym and sym), 1685 (str. vib. of C=O of oxime), 1625 (str. vib. of C=O of amide), 1597-1546 (str. vib. of C=C arom). ¹H-NMR spectra recorded the following signals; 4.12 (singlet, 2H, CH₂-S), 7.28-7.30 (doublet, 2H, CH far C=O), 7.31-7.82 (multiplet, 4H, CH of benzothiazole), 7.91-7.94 (doublet, 2H, CH near C=O), 8.35 (singlet, 1H, NH of amide group), 9.35 (singlet, 1H, NH of oxime), 10.78 (singlet, 1H, OH). ¹³C-NMR spectra recorded the following signals; 41.12 (CH₂-S), 116.28-137.12 (CH arom), 153.61 (C=N of benzothiazole), 158.62 (C=O of amide), 167.22 (C=O of oxime).